

PRINCIPLES FOR COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: *This article discusses about communicative learning and teaching of the English language in modern classroom. The author gives some useful methods and ways of improving speaking skills, group works , activities which are aimed for improving students' pronunciation, grammar and listening skills, as well.*

Key words: *Communicative Language Teaching, facilitate learning, classroom activities, fluency, accuracy, techniques, strategies, puzzles, task – based learning, student centered learning.*

Communicative language learning can be understood as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom [Jack C. Richards,2]. Students in Communicative language (CLT) teaching classroom feel more responsibility for their learning and teacher is a monitor of facilitator. Advantages of CLT in the classroom activities include cooperative work and the conversation as a must.

Littlewood W. [1981] groups classroom activities into two kinds: Pre-communicative activities and Communicative activities. The first group consists of structural and quasi-communicative activities and the second one includes functional communication and social interactional communication activities. In the most books on CLT practice the activities focused on fluency and accuracy. As the classroom activities are based on communication the authenticity, that is to say real world sources become the flagman of all learning process.

We need innovative methods and techniques in teaching English to learn the language easier. A lot of changes have taken place in education system of Uzbekistan. Radical transformation have altered the appearance of the modern world. According to them we discover the best ways of teaching and learning. Much attention is being paid to learning foreign language in our country. Cooperative learning is the innovative model of teaching English. Johnson and Johnson shows five features of successful cooperative learning activity:

1. Students learn that their success depends upon working together interdependently;
2. Students are individually accountable while achieving group goals;
3. Students support and assist one another's success through face-to-face interactions;

4. Students develop social skills by cooperating and working together effectively;

5. Students as a group have the opportunity to reflect on the effectiveness of working together.

When these principles are realized, cooperative learning creates a rich environment for students to learn language. Students can reap all of these benefits by working cooperatively in the classroom. But it is not easy to interact in groups. For example, in jigsaw activity, students are divided into groups of four to complete a puzzle. Each group receives a complete puzzle and each member of the group receives one fourth of the puzzle's piece in a bag. The challenge is for the group of students to complete the puzzle without touching or moving each other's puzzle pieces. They may discuss puzzle piece placement with each other, but each person is in charge of assembling his or her individual puzzle pieces within the whole puzzle.

In addition to that, students need to be allowed to develop their oral language and critical thinking skills by challenging each other through discussions. By changing the culture of the classroom, students will have opportunity to practice the skills of cooperation, tolerance of ideas and multiparty group communication that are so valuable when participating in cooperative learning. The learning environment for cooperative learning is characterized by democratic processes and active roles for students in deciding what should be studied and how.

Conversational competence is a complex set of abilities that involves many components, including pronunciation, listening and grammar skills. Group work is an essential activity in a conversation course because the kind of conversational interaction produced in group activities has been shown to quantitatively as well as qualitatively different from that which goes on in teacher-dominated lessons. In group works, students do all of the talking, and students often do little more than respond to Wh or Yes-No questions. In group works, students do all of the talking and have to take the responsibility for using conversational resources to complete a task. Students thus not only get more opportunities to speak, but they also have the chance to use and practice a great variety of conversational strategies than they would in traditional class activities. This type of activities provides opportunities for development of grammatical proficiency, vocabulary, discourse strategies, strategies of social interaction, and awareness of cross-cultural differences. Students want to become enthusiastically and authentically involved. They want to know that they are genuinely respected and treated as individuals by their teachers and classmates. Restructuring activity category or strategy improves speaking skills of students. The objectives and formats are as follows: 1. To break down expected classroom structures. 2. To create opportunities for supportive behavior. 3. To dispel fears and anxieties. 4. To relax both the student and the teacher. Restructuring activities usually require the students to get up and out of their chairs, to interact physically as a group [2]. There is minimal participation by the teacher. Often the communication is done non-verbally, through action, drawing, or quick written statements, and is usually non-personal.

Teaching English in groups for enhancing and retraining of nurses and pharmaceutical specialists, as with many other educational centers and establishments, requires a slightly different approach, owing to a high non-native English speakers or listeners. In a typical classroom or group, some students may be fluent high-level achievers, others at an intermediate level, and even are still at a beginner level. With these class dynamics at play, the class teacher has to decide whether the chosen lesson Curriculum will be relevant to all students. In my own practice, I have used audio and video recordings with materials for beginners and intermediate level for improving their listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. Students learned given materials very easy and simple way. The more they listened to English texts, pronunciation, speaking, songs, the more they understood English speech.

The research on language learners and language learning argues against a single “method” for teaching a foreign language. [4] The needs and feelings of the language student and his success in acquiring the target language must be the primary considerations. The contribution that the teacher will make in guiding the learner, not only in terms of grammatical explanations, but in every aspect of language teaching, should be dependent upon the unique qualities of individual learners. This research supports the methods of communicative and task – based learning in the English classroom. In the setting of teaching English as a Foreign Language, became evident that a student-centered environment facilitated a new appreciation for the necessary skills to survive in the country where a different native language is spoken.

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